

THE INFLUENCE OF LIGHT ON NITROGEN FIXATION IN DACCA SOIL.

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Experiments have been made with Dacca soil with an organic carbon content of 365 mg per 100 g. of soil according to conditions as laid down by Dhar for the fixation of nitrogen in presence of carbohydrates.

In recent years Dhar ("Presidential Address of the National Academy of Sciences, India," Jan., 1937; Dhar and Mukerji, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 15, 543) has put forward the view that nitrification in soils and nitrogen fixation from the atmosphere are, especially in the tropics, photochemical, at least so far as bacterial action goes. This postulation, if established, will open a new chapter at least so far as the tropical countries are concerned. According to Dhar, substances rich in carbohydrates like butter, ghee (clarified butter), sodium tartrate, citrate, oleate, palmitate, stearate, canesugar, glycerol, molasses, etc., when mixed with soil and exposed to air and light are oxidised on the soil surface and causes nitrogen fixation. It was felt desirable to examine as to how far the influence of light causes nitrogen fixation in Dacca soil in presence of carbohydrates. Canesugar was chosen as the carbohydrate in this investigation. The Dacca soil which was selected for experiments on nitrogen fixation, had an organic carbon content of 365 mg. per 100 g. of soil and the pH of the soil was 5.2. The total nitrogen content of the soil was 48 mg. per 100 g. of oven-dry soil. The same sample was used throughout. It was found by experiment that the soil did not contain any *azotobacter*.

EXPERIMENTAL.

600 G. of soil were thoroughly mixed with 12 g. of canesugar separately in two dishes. One of the dishes with its contents was exposed to ordinary sunlight daily for eight hours, whilst the other was wrapped round with black cloth to exclude light and kept outside along with the exposed one to eliminate the temperature factor. The moisture was made up to 20% at the beginning to mix the ingredients properly. As there is considerable evaporation, more so in light than in the dark, dishes were weighed and the requisite amount of distilled water was added daily to the

exposed dish and after three days to the dish kept to the dark, so as to keep a uniform moisture content of 16% throughout the experiment. From time to time weighed portions of samples were taken out and analysed for ammonia nitrogen, nitrate nitrogen, total nitrogen as well as total carbon and percentage moisture. The determinations of the percentages of ammonia nitrogen and of nitrate nitrogen in the soils were carried out by following the method devised by Oslen (*Compt. rend. trav. lab. Carlsburg*, 1929, 17, No. 15). The percentages of total nitrogen were determined by Kjeldahl's method, whereas the percentages of total carbon by following the wet combustion method devised by Walkley (*J. Agric. Sci.*, 1935, 28, 598). The percentages of moisture in the soils were determined by keeping a small quantity of weighed soil in an electric oven at about 105° for a period of nearly 20 hours, and then finding out the loss in weight.

The results are shown in Tables I and II. Figures in the tables present the amount of nitrogen fixed in mg. per 100 g. of oven-dry soil.

TABLE I.

Exposed to sunlight daily for 8 hours (Temp. 30°–45°) (600 g. soil + 12g. caanesugar.) Started on 10th February, 1939.

Nitrogen fixed per g. of carbon oxidised = 5.7 mg.

(Figures are in mg. per 100 g. oven-dry soil.)

Date of sampling.	NH ₃ -N.	NO ₃ -N.	Total N.	Total C.
Original soil.	1.1	0.9	48.0	365.0
13-3-39	1.1	0.9	48.0	1062.2
18-4-39	1.2	0.9	48.6	906.6
22-5-39	1.2	1.0	49.4	858.7
26-6-39	1.3	1.0	49.8	743.2
22-7-39	1.2	1.0	49.8	694.2

TABLE II.

Dark (Temp. 30°–45°) (600 g. soil + 12g. cane sugar). Started on the 10th February, 1939.

Nitrogen fixed per g. of carbon oxidised = 3.3 mg.

(Figures are in mg. per 100 g. of oven-dry soil.)

Date of sampling.	NH ₄ -N.	NO ₃ -N.	Total N.	Total C.
Original soil.	1.1	0.9	48.0	365.0
13-3-39	1.1	0.9	48.0	1113.1
18-4-39	1.1	0.9	48.2	973.2
22-5-39	1.2	1.0	48.8	905.3
26-6-39	1.2	1.0	48.3	827.7
22-7-39	1.2	0.9	49.2	756.6

The results in Tables I and II show that more carbon is oxidised from the soil treated with canesugar, when it is kept in the light than that when kept in the dark. It is also found that the content of nitrogen in the soils slightly increases both in the light and in the dark. In general, however, the percentages of total nitrogen in the samples exposed to light, are higher than those of the corresponding samples kept in the dark.

Thanks of the author are due to Dr. J. K. Chowdhury and to Dr. S. P. Raychaudhuri for their kind interest during the progress of this work. The author is grateful to the Government of Bengal, for the award of a Research Scholarship which has enabled him to carry out this work.

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Received September 27, 1940.